

Digital Twin supported Structural Health Monitoring of Test Rigs for Wave Energy Applications

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ABSTRACT

The objective of this paper is to document the development and application process of a generic Digital Twin (DT) test rig model for Structural Health Monitoring (SHM). The test rig used for Wave Energy Converter (WEC) component testing is represented by a Component Mode Synthesis (CMS) reduced assembly FEM applicable to real time execution. The Finite Element (FE) simulation model can be exported as a Digital Twin model through a Functional Mockup Unit (FMU) to the digital framework for Dual Hardware in the Loop (DHIL) simulations. The simulation model is also used to generate a Reduced Order Model (ROM). A digital framework can be configured to simultaneously execute and sample data from physical and virtual FMU/ROM sensors on the WEC test rig during tests.

The digital twin model can run in both real time and off-line mode. In real time mode, the physical test rig excitations are sampled and streamed to the digital twin model using open software solutions. Real-time stress and fatigue analysis for the selected load cases can be conducted using virtual strain gauges located at hot spots and identified by a virtual brittle lacquer technique. The streamed data is also buffered and stored on (csv) files for later digital twin off-line execution.

The digital framework supporting data sampling, visualization, analytics, event handling, anomaly detection and digital twin execution is based on open-source Python and Streamlit scripts. The digital twin model is prepared and executed by the open-source FEDEM software [Stranden Ø. et al., 2023] based on both live streaming and historical data. A new two-step FMU and ROM process is developed and applied for DHIL execution.

KEY WORDS: Wave Energy Converter, Digital Twin, FEA, Fatigue

NOMENCLATURE

FEDEM	Open FEA software for flexible mechanism analysis
SHM	Structural Health Monitoring
CMS	Component Mode Synthesis (Reduction)
IMPACT	European Union's Horizon 2020 research project

INTRODUCTION

This paper presents a methodology for Digital Twin-based real time Structural Health Monitoring (SHM) of a Dual Hardware-In-the-Loop (DHIL) testing platform using open-source FEDEM and Phyton software tools. Contrary to recently applied SHM methods based on Machine Learning (ML) [Lai et al., 2023] [Tran. et al., 2024], these tools offer real time calculation of stresses in hotspots identified by a virtual brittle lacquer and physical test loads. The FEDEM tools also support easy repositioning of strain gages when new test rig configurations are used.

The framework targets dynamic components and subsystems testing of Wave Energy Converters (WECs). The testing platform is configurable for DHIL testing of different WEC types and hence able to simulate a wide range of dynamic environment and response loads arising from waves, currents, and wind excitations, including the effects of mooring and electrical grid. These loads determine the test rig's structural durability and accuracy during long-term WEC testing. Real time simulation of strain time histories from virtual strain gages applied in [Rølvåg et al., 2019] is therefore combined with FMU co-simulation and a new Reduced Order Model approach (ROM). Even though FEDEM supports real time calculation of strain time histories, the proposed ROM has major benefits in stress prediction of complex but linear structures represented by super elements.

The paper is organized into the physical and DT supported DHIL framework, physical asset (WEC), DT model, SHM methods, theory, and results sections. The method and theory section documents two different approaches; a) a linear DT based on the unit load method providing a Reduced Order Model (ROM) of the physical WEC and b) a non-linear DT method based on a FEDEM FMU co-simulation model. Both approaches can be applied in real time hotspot stress calculations during DHIL testing. The theory and method section addresses the applied FEA formulations, CMS based model reduction and strain gage calculations, flexible body dynamic simulation implemented in the SHM framework. The results section demonstrates the FMU and ROM real time capabilities in a SHM framework with respect to stress predictions.

DIGITAL TWIN FRAMEWORK

The VGA test rig instrumentation is comprehensive [Alessandri et al., 2023] but due to the reproduction of FLS and ULS loads from measured sea states a Digital Twin model for Structural health Monitoring (SHM) was established. The DT model is used to generate one FMU and one look-up table (ROM) for real-time simulations. The ROM is a matrix calculated by the unit load method and the FMU is a zip file including predefined inputs, outputs, the model and the open-FEDEM solver. The objective was to complement the physical sensor data with virtual strain gage data for FLS fatigue analysis and ULS failure mode prediction. The virtual strain gages are defined by 3-4 selected nodes, the FEM material, and local directions defined by element edges or nodes.

The DT inputs are forces from the linear WEC actuator and fleet/twist pushrod strokes measured by physical sensors. Both the FMU and ROM are based on open standards and hence compatible with the HIL control software.

The strain gauges can easily be redistributed for different test rig configurations and real time stress calculations as shown in Figure 1. The physical test rig will later be instrumented with strain gages for model verifications.

Figure 1. Main structural test rig components

The structural components test rig acquires data from different transducers/sensors during the DHIL tests, but only the measured reaction forces in the main linear actuator shown in Figure 2 are used as live inputs to the DT model. These dynamic reaction forces are generated by the belt while rotating around the sheaves to adjust fleet and twist angles (according to the configurations to be tested). The pushrod strokes are kept constant during each test configuration.

Initial gravity and pretension forces are also applied to the belt by positioning the main linear actuator and pushrods based on the physical test setup (Twist “X”, Fleet “Y”).

Figure 2. Main linear actuator with load cell

DIGITAL TWIN MODEL – FE STRUCTURES

The test rig is designed to comply with testing of various WEC types. In this paper we will focus on a WEC with a belt configuration. The test rig is therefore modelled and physically assembled with the standard longitudinal frame, carriage and test cell complemented with a belt fleet and twist system of pulleys and pushrods. This system is enforcing misalignments to the belt while it's rotated by an electric motor. Tension is applied by a linear actuator shown in Figure 2. The main structural test rig components in the WEC belt testing configuration are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Main structural test rig components

DIGITAL TWIN MODEL – BELT ALIGNMENT

In the IMPACT project [Alessandri et al., 2023], a transmission belt has been selected as a candidate for the primary mooring element. Testing is required to ensure the product is suitable for the application given the non-standard function and load-case. The primary concern for failure is fatigue driven primarily by tensile cycles. Although the digital twin setup presented in this paper is applicable to the belt test specimen, the digital twin based SHM approach presented in this paper is designed for the test rig and not the WEC mooring elements. The simulated test setup is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Belt fleet and twist adjustment mechanism.

The fleet and twist angles are adjusted by 7 pushrods kept constant during each test configuration as shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Belt fleet and twist pushrods modeled as spring actuators.

DIGITAL TWIN MODEL – ASSEMBLY FEM

The individual test rig components are meshed in NX and positioned in the FEDEM assembly as shown in Figure 6. The NX assembly FEMs are imported to FEDEM as 29 component FEMs. The component FEMs are connected with various joint types to create a fully functional mechanical system. FE nodes connected to joints, springs, sensors, or strain rosettes are automatically defined as external nodes in FEDEM. CMS model reduction is then applied to all component FEMs. The CMS retains all external nodes and eliminates all internal nodes and hence reduces the number of nodes from 2.604.334 to 225 (99.99% reduction) without losing accuracy. The FEDEM model size is further reduced by the master and slave joint constraints.

This CMS nodal reduction is transforming the full FEMs to a set of static and dynamic modes which is enabling both the flexible and rigid body part of the mechanical system motion. To increase the simulation accuracy, 4 dynamic component modes with fixed external nodes (supernodes) are added to the flexible belt. The mesh summary is shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Assembly FEM summary

Assembly mesh info	# Nodes
No of Nodes before CMS	2 604 334
No of Nodes after CMS	225
No of system DOFs to solve	667

A CMS based method proposed in [Rølvåg et.al., 2019] also enables real time calculation of strain and stresses in strain rosettes due to precomputed matrices mapping rosette leg stresses directly from external node displacements. This transformation is enabling a real time co-simulation performance of strain time histories for fatigue analysis.

However, a faster ROM can be obtained by combining FEDEM and the unit-loads method when the model is almost linear. This technique is presented in a later section.

Figure 6. The FEDEM assembly FEM.

DIGITAL TWIN MODEL – HOT SPOT IDENTIFICATION

The test rig configuration has a major impact on the structural health of the Carriage, Longitudinal frame, and Test cell structures. The identification of hot-spots is therefore only based on the accumulated damage due to the measured loads applied in the physical belt WEC testing. The accumulated damage due to all load combined in a "Duty Cycle" is calculated by a virtual brittle lacquer applied on the FEDEM test rig model as described in [Rølvåg et.al, 2017].

Figure 7. Strain rosette distribution in calculated hotspots.

The strain gauges are then located in the hot-spots with the highest accumulated damage as shown in Figure 7. The strain gauges are located and oriented by 4 selected nodes and a user defined local coordinate. Nine hot-spots are monitored by collocated strain gages of type "triple gage 45". The strain gauges with leg directions are shown as black symbols below. These 8 strain rosettes add another 24 DOFs to the 667 system DOFs (3 legs /rosette).

DIGITAL TWIN – FMU METHOD AND THEORY

To enable real time Digital Twin solver performance, FEDEM is using a super element technology based on the CMS model reduction technique. This technology also enables real time stress and strain calculations as shown in [Rølvåg et.al, 2017 and T. Moi et al., 2019].

The CMS method establishes a static relationship (modes) between the external and internal nodes. These static modes are used by FEDEM to compute both the rigid body motion captured by co-rotated frames and the flexible motion, e.g. the elastic displacements relative to the corotated frames. For slender structures like the WEC belt, additional fixed interface normal/dynamic modes are added to capture internal component vibrations due to excitations from the external supernodes. The basic CMS method is given by

$$\mathbf{v}_{free} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{v}_e \\ \mathbf{v}_i \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{I} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{B} & \mathbf{\Phi} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{v}_e \\ \mathbf{y} \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{[H]} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{v}_e \\ \mathbf{y} \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{v}_e are the external supernode displacements and \mathbf{y} are the component mode (Φ) amplitudes contributing to the elastic displacements \mathbf{v}_{free} in the condensed internal degrees of freedom \mathbf{v}_i for one FE component. The static modes are stored in the columns of \mathbf{B} and the fixed interface normal modes are stored in $\mathbf{\Phi}$. This model reduction enables real time simulation performance independent of the size of the component FEMs.

The CMS method was further developed [Rølvåg et.al, 2017] in real time calculation of stresses in structural hotspots by strain rosettes. The hot spots are identified by a virtual brittle-lacquer technique frequently used in experimental stress analysis. The method relies on cracking of a layer of brittle coating which is applied to the surface under investigation [Hearn et al., 1997]. The coating is normally sprayed onto the surface and cracks will occur on the hot spots during physical fatigue testing.

A “digital twin” version of this technique presented in [Rølvåg et. Al, 2019] wraps a layer of “Strain Coat Elements” around each structural FEM model is applied on the WEC test rig. One strain coat element is created for each non-interior face of the finite elements. When the belt loads are applied, the Strain Coat Analysis recovers the stresses and strains on all strain coat elements in the test rig model as shown in Figure 6. The strain coat and fatigue analysis process based on strain rosettes is given in [Rølvåg et. Al, 2019] and the CMS based equation (2) that calculates strain time histories in real time is given by

$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{rosette} = [\mathbf{T}_{re} \tilde{\mathbf{B}} \mathbf{T} \mathbf{A} \mathbf{L} \mathbf{H}] \mathbf{v}_{sup} = \quad (2)$$

Where \mathbf{H} is the CMS matrix in Eq. (1), \mathbf{L} is recovering all internal nodal DOFs from possible linear couplings, \mathbf{A} is extracting displacements for all (3 or 4) nodes used to define the strain rosette element, \mathbf{T} is transforming the displacements to local strain rosette leg directions, $\tilde{\mathbf{B}}$ is the strain-displacement matrix given by the derivatives of the strain element shape functions, and \mathbf{T}_{re} is the cartesian to rosette coordinate system transformation matrix. The strains $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{rosette}$ in the rosette coordinate system can finally be directly related to the FE superelement DOFs \mathbf{v}_{sup} as shown in eq. (2). E.g. If the component FEM has two external super nodes (12 DOFs) and two single leg strain rosettes (2 DOFs), $[\mathbf{T}_{re} \tilde{\mathbf{B}} \mathbf{T} \mathbf{A} \mathbf{L} \mathbf{H}]$ becomes a 2x12 matrix independent of the original unreduced component FEM.

Eq. (2) is precomputed only once for each strain gauge element which allows real time calculations and SHM of hot spot strains during digital twin mechanism simulations. The elapsed dynamic solver time for a 1923 second physical test event sampled and simulated at 10Hz was only

545 seconds. The elapsed time includes simultaneous calculations of eq. (2), ROM execution, and visualization of gage stresses. The simulations were executed on a laptop workstation.

The nonlinear dynamic FEDEM equations are written on incremental form and solved by the Newmark- β time integration algorithm with respect to the external node displacement increments $\Delta \mathbf{r}_k$ for time increment k .

$$\mathbf{M}_k \Delta \ddot{\mathbf{r}}_k + \mathbf{C}_k \Delta \dot{\mathbf{r}}_k + \mathbf{K}_k \Delta \mathbf{r}_k = \Delta \mathbf{Q}_k \quad (3)$$

where \mathbf{M}_k , \mathbf{C}_k , and \mathbf{K}_k are the system mass, damping and stiffness matrices respectively reduced by the CMS method. $\Delta \mathbf{Q}_k$ is the vector of applied incremental loads during $\Delta \mathbf{r}_k$. To achieve equilibrium at the end of the time increment k , Newton-Raphson iterations are used to minimize the residual forces. The non-linear solution process is given in [Sivertsen, 2001]. The model and solver setup with predefined physical actuator inputs and virtual strain gage outputs are finally exported from FEDEM as an FMU file applicable to hardware in the loop simulations.

In general, all FEDEM inputs from physical assets must be tagged as actuators, and all results can be tagged as sensors and hence defined as FMU inputs and outputs.

DIGITAL TWIN - ROM METHOD AND THEORY

The costs of using a licensed FMU in a Digital Twin setup are sometimes a concern. Although FEDEM became an open-source software [Stranden et Al., 2023], the authors wanted to benchmark a Reduced Order Model (ROM) concept based on the up front FEDEM simulations and the unit load method [D. Janjic et al., 2002].

The reaction load measured by a load cell mounted on the linear actuator can be used to estimate the tension of the belt and the structural WEC rig loads. During a physical test, the pushrod lengths are constant, and a linear cylinder displacement is applied by the actuator. The measured force is also applied in the digital twin simulations. The deviation shown in Figure 8 is caused by the lack of detailed properties of the transmission belt. In this study the deviation is acceptable since the authors focus on the SHM of the test rig and not the belt.

Figure 8. Linear cylinder stroke during physical and simulated test.

The limited cylinder stroke and constant pushrod lengths indicate a linear behavior of the test rig that makes the unit load method applicable. A cylinder unit load is therefore applied in combination of zero fleet pushrod extension while solving eq. (2) in FEDEM. The output gage stresses then become a linear function of the applied cylinder force. This linear relationship between the input force and gage stresses can be expressed by the corresponding stress/force relationship for all 9 gages

(ref. "FORCE GAINS" in Figure 9). This estimation is valid until the yield strength is reached. These gains are calculated in a separate simulation with a constant unit input load and zero pushrod extension.

The fleet pushrod adjustment also influences the gage stresses. The relationship between pushrod extension and gage stresses is therefore assumed to be linear until yield stresses occur. A separate simulation is therefore executed to monitor the 9 gage stresses while linearly applying maximum pushrod extension with zero linear cylinder force and displacement. This gave the stress/displacement relationships for all 9 gages (ref. "STROKE GAINS" in Figure 9). The estimated STROKE and FORCE gains are given in Table 2.

Table 2. The Estimated ROM / look up table.

GAGE ID	STROKE GAIN	FORCE GAIN
1	6,718E+00	9,842E+01
2	9,117E+02	2,050E+02
3	1,069E+03	1,275E+02
4	3,673E+03	1,018E+02
5	7,214E+03	3,544E+02
6	2,335E+03	9,787E+01
7	8,825E+01	1,111E+02
8	1,283E+03	2,471E+02
9	2,693E+02	1,516E+02

The estimated ROM (2x9) look up table can be multiplied with the actual test cylinder forces and pushrod extensions to give an estimate of the hot spot stresses. This multiplication is easier to implement and faster to run in most IoT systems compared to the FEDEM FMU. In this study, the ROM is implemented and benchmarked in the FEDEM control system as shown in Figure 9. This implementation provides simultaneously execution and easy comparison between the FMU and ROM based hot spot gage stresses.

Figure 9. ROM simulation with the FEDEM control system.

RESULTS

This paper focuses on an open software framework embedding different digital twin methods and tools. Both the supporting R&D project

[IMPACT project, 2024] and the physical test rigs were delayed one year due to late hardware deliverables from suppliers. Only limited sets of measured physical actuator forces and pushrods displacements were available before submitting this paper.

The quality of these data was acceptable since the belt acted like a low pass filter removing the high frequency content of the measured reaction loads. The resulting simulated stress time variations from the virtual strain gages are therefore reliable even though they are still not validated by the physical strain gages on the WEC hardware. The validation will be completed for three physical test rig configurations and presented at the ISOPE 2024 conference. The physical tests will be documented and recorded on videos available on request after this event. This paper will therefore document and validate the stress time histories calculated by the two reduced order different digital twin models (FMU versus ROM).

To compare and validate the ROM accuracy against the FMU simulation model, the calculated stress time histories were plotted in Figure 10. To mimic the initial rig setup, the pushrod stroke giving the fleet adjustment was applied in the equilibrium iteration. The WEC rig strain gages were therefore prestressed as indicated in Figure 10. The FMU stress time histories are shown in the colored curves while the corresponding ROM estimated stresses are shown as dark grey curves.

Both approaches represent reduced order models providing stresses in real time, sampled, and simulated at the same frequency (100 Hz) without any influence of the FEM size. The time delay due to data handling and processing is dependent on the edge computer. Cloud computers are only used for offline simulations and long-term data storage.

Figure 10. Stresses calculated by the FEDEM FMU and ROM matrix.

The FMU simulated and ROM estimated results shown in Figure 10 are basically identical except for gages no. 1, 2, 8 and 9 where a minor deviation is observed. The deviation is in all practical terms neglectable, but possible to eliminate by expanding the ROM look up table with a third dimension. The minor non-linearities in the FE model can be captured by new tabulated gain sets representing different ranges of cylinder forces and pushrod displacements. The total hotspot stress

execution time, e.g. solving eq (2) 19230 times was only 4.1 seconds for a FE assembly model with 2.6 million nodes. That execution time includes both FMU and ROM based stress calculations and simultaneously plotting of Figure 10.

The complete stress distribution can also be executed and visualized or animated in an IoT browser at selected time steps capturing the most critical ULS load conditions. A stress plot representing the worst-case simulated load step is shown in Figure 11. This is a postprocessing task that has to be performed by a FEDEM batch simulation on a cloud server due to FMU restrictions.

Figure 11. ULS/Worst case stress distribution.

CONCLUSION

In this paper, two Digital Twin models represented by the FMU simulation model, and the ROM look up table are presented and validated. The accuracy of the estimated ROM and hence strain gage stresses are applicable to most SHM tasks. The remaining Rainflow and fatigue analysis shown in [Rølvåg et al., 2019] are postprocessing tasks that can be performed in real time but more likely once per hour, day or week on an IoT cloud server. A full FEA of critical ULS loads identified by an event trigger in the IoT framework should also run off-line. These are tasks that will be implemented and verified before the [IMPACT, 2024] project is terminated.

The main advantage of using the Digital Twin models in SHM is unlimited number of virtual strain gages which are easy to redistribute without additional hardware or implementation costs. The virtual strain gages can also be applied in hostile environments, and they are not affected by temperature variations.

This study is based on the open source FEDEM software designed for real time DHIL digital twin simulation supporting Condition (CM) and Structural Health Monitoring (SHM). The software also supports FMU export and easy generation of Reduced Order Models (ROM). Both approaches are compatible with most IoT frameworks. The FMU approach is based on the FMI standard [FMI, 2024] supporting real time co-simulation of non-linear systems. The ROM can be represented by a look up table applicable to linear systems in any IoT system without FMU support. In our further IMPACT work, we will implement the FMU solution in an open-source Python / Streamlit IoT framework.

FURTHER WORK

The Digital Twin test rig framework in Figure 1 will be implemented before the R&D project [IMPACT, 2024] is terminated. The results will be embedded in the ISOPE 2024 conference presentation. Two other WEC test rig configurations will also be validated before and presented

at the conference. Videos presenting the SHM framework and results will be recorded during the physical and virtual test rig benchmarks. These will be posted on the author's YouTube channel.

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